

The SELFNET approach to Self-Protection through Autonomic Network Management

Maria João Barros, Anastasius Gavras
Eurescom GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany

Gregorio Martinez Perez, Manuel Gil Pérez
University of Murcia, Spain

Jose Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang,
University of the West of Scotland, Paisley,
Renfrewshire, UK

Pedro Neves, Rui Calé
Altice Labs (Portugal Telecom Inovação), Aveiro,
Portugal

Abstract—The 5G infrastructure initiative in Europe [1] has agreed a number of very challenging key performance indicators (KPIs) to significantly enhance the user experience and support a number of use cases, among others to provide self-protection capabilities for detecting and mitigating potential cyber-attacks. At the same time there is high pressure on the reduction of the operational expenditure (OPEX). A contribution to meeting the KPIs and to reduce OPEX is to evolve the management of the network into a fully autonomic and intelligent framework. Based on advanced technologies, such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV), the EU H2020 project SELFNET [2] is proposing a sophisticated management framework to achieve these objectives. This paper briefly introduces the project, its architectural approach and elaborates on the self-protection use case that serves validation purposes.

Keywords—Autonomic management, self-protection, software defined networking, network function virtualisation, 5G network infrastructure

I. INTRODUCTION

Advances in mobile technologies and the user-driven growth of services require the inception of a new generation of network management mechanisms able to support these new mobile technologies, services and applications. The SELFNET project is designing and implementing an autonomic network management framework to provide Self-Organising Network (SON) capabilities in new 5G infrastructures. By automatically detecting and mitigating a range of common network problems, SELFNET provides a management framework that significantly reduces operational costs, contributes to faster service provisioning and improves user/customer experience.

II. THE SELFNET PROJECT

By exploring the integration of advanced technologies such as SDN, NFV, SON, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence, SELFNET provides a scalable, extensible and smart network management system.

The framework assists network operators to perform key management tasks such as automatic deployment of SDN/NFV applications that provide automated network monitoring and autonomic network maintenance, delivered by defining high-

level tactical measures and enabling autonomic corrective and preventive actions to mitigate existing or potential network problems.

SELFNET address major network management concerns by providing self-protection capabilities against distributed network attacks, self-healing capabilities against network failures, and self-optimisation features to dynamically improve network performance and the QoE of the users.

III. SELFNET ARCHITECTURAL STANDARD FOUNDATIONS

The SELFNET architecture takes into account the requirements expressed by the SELFNET use cases, and is aligned with the most relevant standards which are the foundations of the project, namely ETSI NFV [3], Open Networking Foundation (ONF) [4] and TeleManagement Forum (TMF) [5].

ETSI NFV [3] is standardising the virtualization of Networks Functions (NFs). It defines the complete architecture required to accommodate the challenges of the virtualization paradigm. The architecture covers runtime and management aspects for the entire lifecycle of a Virtual Network Function (VNF). It also covers the management of network services, which are built by orchestrating multiple VNFs, according to a forwarding graph, using a catalogue-driven approach.

ONF [4] is self-described as “an organization devoted to promote the utilization of software-defined technologies to program the network”. Following an SDN approach, the network is separated into three different parts: the user-data plane, the controller plane and the control plane. The user-data plane is responsible for forwarding the user traffic, while the controller plane is composed by SDN controllers which provide high-level APIs to the control plane above. The control plane programs the network, easing the creation of new applications and speeding up the rollout of new services.

The TMF is a telecom industry association that provides guidelines helping operators to create and deliver profitable services. A major achievement is the definition of the telecom business process (eTOM) and application (TAM) maps, which include all activities related to a telecommunications operator. In order to accommodate the SDN/NFV impact, the TMF has created the Zero-touch Orchestration, Operations and

Management (ZOOM) program [5] that builds more dynamic support systems, fostering service and business agility.

A. Combining SDN & NFV

NFV and SDN have been created by different standards bodies. However, they are complementary technologies, thus are often referred to as NFV/SDN. The NFV technology enables the creation of new network functions on-demand and placing them on the most suitable location, using the most appropriate amount of resources. This possibility is facilitated by SDN, which enables network (re)configuration and (re)sequencing (chaining) of functions.

Currently no agreed architecture is available, which seamlessly integrates NFV and SDN. For supporting its objectives, the SELFNET project defined a combined architecture that use the ETSI NFV architecture as a baseline and introduces the SDN paradigm. The resulting architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. NFV and SDN combined architecture

The combined architecture is compliant with ETSI NFV, while some changes are introduced to accommodate the SDN concept. A naming of the architectural components still needs to be agreed. Currently similar boxes have different names, depending on whether the underlying concepts originate in the NFV world or the SDN world.

In order to support legacy components (non-NFV, non-SDN), the architecture considers Physical Network Functions (PNF), which support neither the NFV nor SDN model. Similarly the architecture considers VNFs with no SDN capabilities. For these functions the VNF naming is retained, as shown in the rightmost side of the dashed square. In the middle, all components are SDN-aware, meaning that they are split into three layers. In the user-data plane there are Network Elements (NEs), which can be Physical Network Elements (PNEs) or Virtual Network Elements (VNEs). In this case, the names are chosen from the SDN world, since they describe the roles they are performing more clearly. On the controller layer, SELFNET may have multiple controllers at different levels, naming all of them as SDN Controllers. Finally, for the control layer, we use the name SDN Application (SDN App).

IV. SELFNET REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The self-organizing capabilities of 5G networks are provided by means of an architecture based on differentiated layers and illustrated in Fig. 2:

Fig. 2. SELFNET Architecture Overview

The following logical high-level scopes are defined in the architecture and briefly explained below:

- **Infrastructure Layer:** contains the Physical Sublayer and the Virtualization Sublayer. The Physical Sublayer contains all physical elements of the network, as well as the physical servers available in the Data Centre (DC). The Virtualization Sublayer provides access to the virtual resources of the DC through a hypervisor. The Virtualization Sublayer represents the NFVI (Network Functions Virtualization Infrastructure) as defined by ETSI NFV.
- **Data Network Layer:** represents the instantiation of the virtual networking infrastructures. The SDN paradigm decouples the control plane functions from the data plane functions, transforming the latter into a simple forwarding layer. Therefore, in order to be fully aligned with SDN, the SON Data Plane Sublayer is explicit in the architecture diagram.
- **Control Layer:** includes two internal sublayers: SDN Controllers Sublayer and SON Control Plane Sublayer. The SDN Controllers Sublayer comprises a group of horizontal and vertically distributed SDN Controllers, whereas the SON Control Plane Sublayer represents the network functions control plane, being either actuators or sensors.
- **SON Autonomic Layer:** includes the mechanisms to provide the network intelligence. It collects pertinent information about the network behaviour, uses that information to diagnose the network condition, and decides what must be done to accomplish the system goals. It then guarantees the organized enforcement of the actions that are determined.
- **NFV Orchestration & Management Layer:** corresponds to ETSI MANO layer, and to its basic functions: VNFs orchestration, VIM and VNF management. It includes the management of the data centres virtual

infrastructure, as well as the inter-data centre network, also known as WAN (Wide Area Network).

- **SON Access Layer:** encompasses the interface functions that are exposed by the framework. Despite the fact that internal components may have specific interfaces for the particular scope of their functions, these components contribute to a general SON API, managed by the SELFNET API Broker Sublayer, that exposes all aspects of the autonomic framework to external actors such as Business Support Systems or Operational Support Systems.

V. SELF-PROTECTION USE CASE SCENARIO

Three user-driven scenarios have been chosen to highlight how each of the components and layers in the SELFNET framework act in concert to meet the SELFNET objectives of self-optimisation, self-healing and self-protection. For each of these objectives one representative scenario has been defined.

The use cases will be used to illustrate the potential and key functionalities of SELFNET. For instance, all use cases aim to achieve reactive, corrective actions as well as proactive, preventive measures against potential or forthcoming network problems or challenges in terms of fault/failure risks, cyber-attacks, QoS/QoE maintenance and enhancement and so on, far beyond the state of the art. The implementation of the use cases serves the validation purpose of the framework.

In this section we elaborate on a representative scenario to demonstrate self-protection against distributed denial of service attacks.

In this scenario the objective is to detect and mitigate the effects of cyber-attacks and restore 5G network traffic to a steady state of security [6]. Early detection of potential cyber-attacks triggers a system reconfiguration in preparation for an imminent attack. Detection and mitigation processes can also be employed proactively. Detection is conducted at two levels of abstraction. In a first stage, a high-level analysis is performed, based only on basic monitoring information of network flows. Once a potential attack is detected, a low-level Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) is triggered. This is achieved by deploying and enforcing a virtualized and personalized honeynet to isolate the attack, while applying countermeasures to protect assets. Due to the massive amount of traffic in the network, deep inspection is not feasible in the first stage.

Specific elements (candidate VNFs) are split across two major phases of the attack detection service lifecycle, namely: (i) sensing, where the system has to deploy traffic monitoring probes to collect and correlate traffic data used to identify cyber-attacks, (ii) actuation, where the system deploys a chain of mitigation VNFs and enforces policies to force malicious traffic to pass through threat management systems where it can be mitigated/filtered. Virtualized network security functions may include DPI, firewall, threat management system, honeynets, intrusion protection system, etc. They can be deployed and chained in data centres and at different locations in the network. They are deployed according to the specific type of protection required at each location, thus building a network for distributed security functions.

The multi-tenant security services concept in this self-protection use case is depicted in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Multi-tenant security services distributed across edge and core

The main idea is that a VNF security service provider, such as the network operator or a security specialist, offers multi-tenant security services to its customers. Virtualized network security functions for security services may include virtual traffic monitor/DPI, virtual firewall, virtual threat management system, virtual honeynets, virtual Intrusion Protection System (IPS), adaptive firewalls, vector attack identification tools etc. These services can be deployed and chained on demand or permanently in data centres at different locations in the network e.g., at the mobile access, Points of Presence (PoPs) or in the core network, in response to distributed attacks or intrusions that could potentially affect all 5G network segments, such as the Radio Access Network (RAN), micro data centres at the PoP, the core network, or the core data centres. The services are selectively and dynamically deployed according to the specific type of protection required at each location, thus building a network of distributed security functions.

Fig. 4. DDoS attack by injecting large volumes of malicious traffic

Although there are potentially a large number of cyber threats involving 5G networks, this use case is focused on DDoS attacks and other types of intrusions such as virus spreading attacks. Fig. 4 illustrates a DDoS attack that is conducted after compromising a number of users' devices for being part of a botnet, executing the actions requested by the botnet controller.

When information on a potential attack is obtained from monitoring and analysis, the SELFNET framework responds twofold: (i) in proactive mode where self-protection actions are triggered before the cyber-attack becomes widely spread, (ii) in reactive mode making use of a Collaborative Intrusion Detection System (CIDS) to detect the source of attack, deploy a honeynet and redirect all affected connections to it by reconfiguring the network flows accordingly.

This process is illustrated in Fig. 5 where the attacker continues its execution over a virtualized network which it is not real.

Fig. 5. Countermeasures by building a honeynet to counter the cyber-attack

The differentiation between high-level network flow analysis and low-level packet inspection allows the proposed multi-level protection scheme to offer the required levels of scalability and granularity in 5G environments.

The following differentiated security VNFs are considered in this use case:

- Backend VNFs: security VNFs deployed in the PoP data centres that aim to provide security functions for PoP-to-PoP and PoP-to-core data centre traffic. These are security functions mostly dedicated to network traffic that stays within the network, such as related to traffic between headquarters.
- Frontend VNFs: security VNFs deployed in the core data centres to provide perimeter security functions. Therefore, these VNFs provide gateway protection functionalities for the tenants' network traffic towards the Internet and vice versa.

Furthermore an additional level of distribution can be implemented on top of this distributed deployment of virtual

functions across different data centres and network locations. The objective of this additional layer is to optimize the performance of security services and to reduce latency. This can be achieved by splitting each virtual function across several child virtual security sensors that are still implemented as VNFs. Each child sensor is responsible for a given set of rules, signatures or traffic types that can then be matched in parallel. A coordination function, possibly deployed as an SDN App, becomes necessary for each virtual security function in the multi-tenant distributed service. This function will coordinate and balance its associated child virtual sensors.

Virtual sensors for security are generally deployed, configured and chained at the instantiation of the service for any given tenant network. However, virtual security actuators are automatically instantiated and configured at the appropriate network location as part of the self-protection approach. This means that, when a sensor VNF detects an intrusion or attack, the SELFNET framework managing and orchestrating the multi-tenant security service can properly react to block and mitigate the attack. Deployment of a new actuator VNF at the right location in the security service chain, including the re-configuration of the chain itself, and deployment of a new sensor VNF specialized for the given traffic pattern or intrusion type are examples of the range of possible reactions.

In this use case, the SELFNET framework also provides automated control and orchestration functions to steer the traffic through distributed VNFs of each tenant. The framework includes self-organization functions that can perform automated reconfiguration of service chains as part of the SELNET response to a cyber-attack.

VI. SELF-PROTECTION REQUIREMENTS

The implementation of the self-protection use case poses a set of challenges that can be briefly summarized with the following keywords: *distribution, multi-tenancy, automated deployment and composition, multi-level and self-learning.*

5G will enable a much higher density of users and devices interconnected at higher data rates, as well as increased mobility and dynamicity than current 4G and fixed networks. For these reasons the self-protection use case requires security functions to be distributed in the 5G network, located close to the vulnerable points and according to the service and user needs. Multi-tenancy is a key property in 5G environments, especially for network and service providers. Security sensors and actuators functions must therefore be implemented as virtualized network functions following the NFV approach and be part of distributed security services running over per-tenant virtualized networks and infrastructures. The combination of a distributed security service with sensors and actuators implemented as VNFs requires a high degree of automation in the deployment of the security VNFs in the virtualized infrastructures. In addition, the framework must also provide automated mechanisms for the composition of individual sensors and actuators, where multiple distributed VNFs are chained and traffic is steered across them to build security services spanning different portions of the 5G networks. A further degree of dynamicity is required here, mostly in support of new actuator VNFs to be dynamically deployed and

included in the distributed service. Upon the detection of a cyber-attack, a prompt re-configuration and re-provisioning of the service chain is required to properly switch the affected traffic to the actuator for mitigation purposes.

Automation and dynamicity requirements, the highly distributed and virtualized approach proposed in the self-protection use case poses scalability and performance challenges, for example when considering traffic monitoring and inspection of 5G ultra high data rates. The implementation of detection and monitoring functions at multiple granularities and levels of abstraction is eminent. On the one end, high-level sensor VNFs are required to provide a first stage of cyber-attacks detection, e.g. by only inspecting network flows. On the other end, low-level and deep traffic inspection virtualized functions are required to provide a second stage of cyber-attacks detection for those network traffic flows already identified as suspect to be under attack. This combined multi-level and multi-granular detection approach allows collecting heterogeneous information about detected attacks, facilitating the implementation of self-learning techniques. Indeed the framework should include learning algorithms and tools with the aim of tuning its protection procedures and decision mechanisms analysing previous attacks and evaluating success or failure of previously applied strategies.

VII. CONCLUSIONS

SELFNET is a scalable, extensible and smart network management architecture which explores the integration of technologies, widely recognized as key enabling technologies for 5G systems, such as SDN, NFV, Self-Organizing Networks

(SON), Cloud Computing, and Artificial Intelligence to implement an autonomic network management system addressing a number of management tasks, such as network monitoring, maintenance, service provisioning and deployment of tools. The paper presented an overview of the architecture which aims to meet the network management objectives of self-optimisation, self-healing and self-protection, based on user-driven scenarios that are representative for each objective.

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